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Effects of International Climate Agreements on Trade in Environmental Goods: The Kyoto Protocol

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Abstract

This study analyzes the impact of international climate agreements—specifically the Kyoto Protocol—on the trade in environmental goods over the period 1997–2021. Using entropy balancing and a sample of 112 countries, we show that the Kyoto Protocol led to an overall increase in the trade of environmental goods among Annex B countries. During this period, the protocol notably stimulated imports, although it did not significantly boost exports prior to 2016. The analysis also highlights heterogeneities linked to countries' technological capacities, economic structures, and institutional characteristics.

Keywords: • Climate Agreements • Environmental Goods • Entropy Balancing

JEL Classification: F18, K32, Q54, Q56

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1 Introduction

Climate change stands today as one of the most pressing challenges facing humanity, with profound implications for ecosystems, societies, and economies. The steady rise in greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions since the Industrial Revolution has led to major climatic disruptions, prompting the need for a coordinated global response. In this context, international agreements such as the Kyoto Protocol (1997) and the Paris Agreement (2016) were established to structure and harmonize global efforts to reduce emissions. The Kyoto Protocol set legally binding targets for industrialized countries, committing them to reduce their greenhouse gas emissions by at least 5% relative to 1990 levels.

Beyond their environmental objectives, these international agreements raise complex economic issues, particularly in the realm of global trade. While trade stimulates economic growth and facilitates the diffusion of technology ([Frankel and Rose, 2005](#)), it also constitutes a significant source of carbon emissions through production processes and cross-border transportation ([Popp, 2006](#)). Paradoxically, trade can also play a key role in the transition to a green economy by promoting the exchange of environmental goods and technologies ([Dechezleprêtre et al., 2013](#)). These exchanges fall within the broader framework of the growing eco-industry sector, which includes firms specializing in the production of goods and services aimed at environmental protection and efficient resource management ([Rennings, 2000](#)). Such goods include renewable energy technologies, energy-efficient equipment, waste management systems, and emissions-reduction technologies—critical tools for addressing climate challenges. However, the implications of international commitments such as the Kyoto Protocol on trade patterns of these goods remain underexplored ([Zugravu-Soilita, 2018](#); [Näher and Schenker-Wicki, 2021](#)).

This study aims to address this gap by examining the impact of the Kyoto Protocol on the trade of environmental goods. The central research question is as follows: *Did the commitments made under the Kyoto Protocol lead to a significant increase in the trade of environmental goods among Annex B countries?* Annex B of the Protocol lists 37 industrialized countries or economies in transition, along with the quantified emission reduction or limitation targets to which they committed. By investigating this issue, we seek to assess whether climate institutional frameworks can foster the development and

diffusion of environmental goods through international trade.

This research contributes to the economic literature in several ways. First, it provides an updated assessment of the impact of international climate agreements on trade structures, with a specific focus on environmental goods—a market segment that remains relatively underexplored. In particular, it highlights the role of the eco-industry in the trade dynamics triggered by such agreements, analyzing how regulatory and economic incentives support the growth of this strategic sector. Second, the study leverages recent data and advanced econometric techniques to isolate the specific effects of the Kyoto Protocol, offering a nuanced perspective on how climate commitments shape trade patterns. Finally, the article offers valuable insights for policymakers by identifying the economic and environmental characteristics of countries that can enhance the effectiveness of climate action.

The results of this study indicate that the entry into force of the Kyoto Protocol led to a significant increase in environmental goods, particularly among Annex B countries. However, this impact is far from uniform. It varies according to several economic, technological, and institutional characteristics. On the one hand, countries with strong green technological intensity, a substantial manufacturing base, or high environmental performance appear to benefit more from the consequences of the Protocol. On the other hand, the effect is amplified in European Union member states as well as in countries that later ratified the Paris Agreement, suggesting a potential spillover effect between successive climate commitments.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature to position our research within the existing theoretical and empirical frameworks. Sections 3 and 4 present the methodological approach and describe the data used for the analysis. Section 5 reports the empirical findings, while Section 7 explores a specific transmission channel. Sections 8 and 6 address the robustness and heterogeneity of the results, respectively. Finally, Section 9 concludes and provides policy recommendations.

2 Literature Review

In this section, we define the Kyoto Protocol and its consequences as discussed in the literature (subsection 2.1). We then present the role of environmental goods in global trade (subsection 2.2). Finally, we examine the literature linking environmental agreements to the trade of environmental goods in the last subsection (2.3).

2.1 The Kyoto Protocol

The Kyoto Protocol, signed in 1997 as a follow-up to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), represents a legally binding attempt at a collective response to climate change. Entering into force in 2005 following Russia’s ratification, it committed 37 industrialized countries—referred to as "Annex B countries"—to collectively reduce their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions by at least 5% below 1990 levels over the period 2008–2012 (Babiker et al., 2000). It marked a major shift in climate governance, explicitly acknowledging the historical responsibility of developed countries in the accumulation of GHGs, while adopting the principle of “common but differentiated responsibilities.”

The Protocol relies on a so-called “flexibility” architecture, designed to minimize the cost of emissions reductions while maximizing economic efficiency. It introduced three main mechanisms: (i) emissions trading, (ii) the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM), which allows a country to finance an emission-reduction project in a developing country and count the resulting reductions toward its own targets, and (iii) Joint Implementation,¹ which is reserved for Annex B countries. These tools were praised for their innovative design but also criticized for their complexity, lack of transparency, and risk of misuse—especially under the CDM, where numerous projects were reportedly approved without generating genuine environmental benefits (Wara, 2007; Michaelowa et al., 2007).

In terms of outcomes, the assessments vary widely. Some studies, such as Maamoun (2019), report a significant decline in emissions in several Annex B countries, partic-

¹Joint Implementation allows an Annex B country to finance an emission-reduction project in another Annex B country and to account for the resulting reductions in its own emissions balance.

ularly in Europe. However, these reductions are sometimes attributed to pre-existing or concurrent structural dynamics, such as deindustrialization or the substitution of coal with natural gas. For instance, Germany largely benefited from reunification and the closure of numerous industrial facilities in the former East Germany. Conversely, [Böhringer and Vogt \(2003\)](#) and [Kim et al. \(2016\)](#) argue that the overall reductions in emissions were modest and largely offset by the lack of participation from major emitters such as the United States, India, and China. Moreover, the targets assigned under the Protocol were not revised despite the rapid evolution of global emissions, which rendered the agreement increasingly obsolete in terms of effective coverage.

From an economic standpoint, the Protocol had a dual impact. On the one hand, it stimulated investment in clean technologies and renewable energy, supported by market-based instruments and incentive policies in some countries. [Babiker et al. \(2000\)](#) estimate that the macroeconomic costs of compliance remained moderate, thanks to the flexibility mechanisms. On the other hand, several studies highlight that the implementation of stricter environmental standards increased production costs for certain energy-intensive industries, revealing sectoral heterogeneity in the impact of the Protocol ([Böhringer and Vogt, 2003](#)). This led to growing concerns about international competitiveness, particularly in the steel, cement, and chemical sectors, sometimes prompting “green relocation” strategies or demands for sectoral exemptions.

One of the most studied effects of the Kyoto Protocol is "carbon leakage"—that is, the relocation of production (and therefore emissions) to countries not bound by the agreement. [Aichele and Felbermayr \(2015b\)](#) show that signatory countries experienced a decline in domestic emissions, but that this reduction was partially offset by an increase in imports from non-committed, often more carbon-intensive countries. This phenomenon suggests that the Kyoto Protocol may have shifted emissions geographically rather than reduced them globally. Their study also reveals a slowdown in exports from energy-intensive industries in committed countries, accompanied by a reorientation of trade flows.

The logic of the Protocol, exempting developing countries from quantified constraints, was intended to uphold climate equity and the right to development. However, this asymmetry generated political tensions. Some industrialized countries, notably the United

States, refused to ratify the agreement precisely due to the lack of symmetrical commitments. Moreover, several developing countries used the CDM mechanisms as a source of financing, sometimes generating projects with limited additionality, or even counter-productive social or environmental outcomes ([Wara, 2007](#)).

Despite its limitations, the Kyoto Protocol laid the groundwork for future climate policy frameworks: it enabled the establishment of national emissions inventories, the standardization of carbon accounting units, and the implementation of environmental policies. These tools influenced several subsequent instruments, including the European Union Emissions Trading System (EU ETS) and the design of the Paris Agreement. The Protocol also highlighted the need for more inclusive and dynamic approaches that go beyond the rigid logic of differentiated quantitative commitments.

2.2 Environmental Goods and Global Trade

The trade in environmental goods has become a strategic lever in the dynamics of ecological transition and green innovation. Its growth in international trade is driven not only by market forces but also by the increasing influence of national and multilateral climate policies. Although definitions vary slightly across institutions, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and the World Trade Organization (WTO) broadly agree in defining environmental goods as products specifically designed to improve environmental quality or reduce the ecological footprint of human activities ([Lee, 2009](#)). These products include industrial pollution control equipment, wastewater treatment plants, renewable energy technologies such as solar panels and wind turbines, as well as low-impact goods like electric vehicles and LED lighting. However, classification remains complex: some products serve both environmental and non-environmental purposes (e.g., pumps, pipes), making categorization problematic. This lack of a uniform nomenclature has slowed international negotiations, notably those initiated under the Environmental Goods Agreement (EGA) led by the WTO ([Balineau and Melo, 2013](#)).

Since the early 2000s, trade in environmental goods has experienced sustained growth. The United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) estimated the global value of environmental goods trade at nearly USD 1.9 trillion in 2022 (represent-

ing 10.7% of manufactured goods trade), with an average annual growth rate exceeding 10%². This dynamic is fueled by increasingly ambitious climate policies, the dramatic drop in the cost of renewable technologies, particularly in solar photovoltaics and LED lighting, and the expanding scope of environment-related markets. The geographical structure of this trade reveals specialization among major economic powers. China holds a dominant position as the world’s leading exporter of green technologies, particularly in solar photovoltaics and battery production. The European Union plays a prominent role in energy efficiency, water treatment, and waste recovery technologies. The United States retains competitive advantages in niche areas such as industrial pollution control, environmental sensors, and energy management software.

The rise of environmental goods trade is heavily shaped by public policies. Production incentives—through manufacturing or export subsidies—have played a decisive role. China, for example, has built its leadership in photovoltaics through substantial state support. In Germany, renewable energy support laws fostered the development of a dense industrial fabric during the 2000s. Stringent environmental regulations, by creating local demand for cleaner technologies, have also stimulated industrial supply (Porter and Van der Linde, 1995; Schott and Jung, 2016). Moreover, multilateral agreements such as the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement have provided normative frameworks that encouraged states to reorient their industrial policies toward sectors aligned with decarbonization goals. Public procurement has also acted as a powerful lever, promoting the adoption of low-carbon technological solutions through government and municipal purchases.

A growing body of empirical work confirms the central role of environmental policies in driving green technology exports. Costantini and Crespi (2010a), using trade data from OECD countries, show that nations with proactive climate policies achieve better export performance in the renewable energy sector than those with weaker or no such regulations. This supports the so-called Porter hypothesis, which argues that well-designed environmental regulation can stimulate innovation and enhance firms’ competitiveness.

Despite this positive momentum, significant obstacles remain. While tariff barriers on environmental goods are generally low (less than 5% on average), non-tariff barriers

²<https://unctad.org/news/global-trade-slows-green-goods-grow>

ers—such as technical requirements, certifications, safety standards, and complex customs procedures—continue to hinder the dissemination of these technologies, particularly toward developing countries (Balineau and Melo, 2013; Schott and Jung, 2016). These countries also face structural constraints: limited industrial capacity, lack of local technological ecosystems, and restricted access to green finance. As a result, they often remain confined to the role of importers, dependent on innovations developed elsewhere.

2.3 Environmental Agreements as a Determinant of Environmental Goods Trade

The relationship between environmental policies and international trade in environmental goods has garnered growing attention in the economic literature, though it remains subject to divergent interpretations. Two main theoretical approaches structure this debate. On one hand, the pollution haven hypothesis posits that firms facing stringent environmental regulations in their home countries may relocate production to jurisdictions with laxer standards, thereby negatively affecting their export competitiveness (Copeland and Taylor, 2003; Antweiler et al., 2001; Levinson and Taylor, 2004; Bovenberg and Smulders, 1995). On the other hand, the Porter hypothesis argues that strict environmental policies can, rather than harming firms, stimulate innovation, improve production efficiency, and ultimately enhance trade performance through the diffusion of clean technologies (Porter and Van der Linde, 1995; Berman and Bui, 2001; Lanoie et al., 2011; Abrell et al., 2011; Löschel et al., 2019; Koch and Themann, 2022).

Empirical findings on this topic are far from conclusive. Some studies, such as Costantini and Crespi (2008, 2010a), reveal a positive correlation between the stringency of environmental regulations and exports of environmental goods. Using a gravity model applied to a panel of OECD countries, these authors show that ambitious climate policies—particularly in Europe—have promoted specialization in green sectors, including renewable energy, energy efficiency technologies, and waste management.

However, other studies provide a more nuanced perspective. Dai et al. (2017), using a panel of Asia-Pacific Economic Cooperation (APEC) member countries, find a potentially regressive effect of stringent environmental norms on green goods exports.

Their analysis suggests that countries subject to stricter constraints may experience a decline in price competitiveness, limiting their ability to succeed in global markets. Similarly, [Cantore and Cheng \(2018\)](#) observe that in some cases, highly regulated developed countries increase their imports of environmental goods rather than fostering domestic production, leading to a substitution effect rather than a crowding-in dynamic.

These empirical contradictions are partly due to the heterogeneity of national contexts. In advanced economies, where research and innovation capacities are already well developed, environmental policies may indeed strengthen comparative advantages in green technologies. [Lanoie et al. \(2011\)](#) support this view, showing that tightening environmental regulations in OECD countries is associated with increased multifactor productivity—a key condition for successful integration into global green technology markets. In contrast, in emerging economies with more limited innovation infrastructure, such policies may have more ambiguous effects. In China, for example, [Wang et al. \(2013\)](#) show that the most ecologically advanced sectors benefit from implicit export support, while more traditional industries under regulatory pressure see their competitiveness decline.

The Kyoto Protocol provides a particularly relevant case for examining the effects of a multilateral environmental policy on trade dynamics. [Tran \(2022\)](#) show that the Protocol’s entry into force was followed by a significant increase, around 30%, in environmental goods exports among Annex B countries. This result is interpreted as evidence that binding commitments can foster industrial repositioning toward green segments. From a complementary perspective, [Miyamoto and Takeuchi \(2018\)](#) identify a positive link between Kyoto ratification and trade in specific technologies, such as wind and solar, especially in pioneering European countries. However, [Aichele and Felbermayr \(2013, 2015b\)](#) offer a more critical reading: their estimates suggest that Kyoto led to increased imports of environmental goods in committed countries, reflecting a form of technological dependence on external suppliers, while also undermining the export performance of energy-intensive sectors. This divergence highlights that trade in green technologies is not solely driven by supply-side dynamics, but also shaped by regulatory-induced transformations in demand.

Finally, the effects of environmental policies also vary significantly across sectors.

Pettersson et al. (2014) show that in highly polluting industries, compliance costs may outweigh productivity gains, resulting in a loss of competitiveness. Conversely, sectors based on breakthrough technologies—such as photovoltaics or smart energy management—tend to benefit more from ambitious policies due to their innovation-intensive structure. This suggests that a differentiated, sector-specific approach to public policy is essential to maximize the commercial benefits.

In sum, although numerous studies have explored the links between environmental regulation and the trade of environmental goods, the findings remain mixed. The specific case of the Kyoto Protocol remains relatively underexplored. Unlike Tran (2022) and Aichele and Felbermayr (2015a), who rely on bilateral trade data, this article uses aggregate trade flows at the country level. First, this approach provides a *global perspective* on environmental trade, allowing us to assess the overall impact of an agreement like the Kyoto Protocol on total trade, rather than limiting the analysis to trade relationships between specific pairs of countries (Anderson and Van Wincoop, 2003).

Second, the analysis of aggregate flows often produces *more robust results*, as it is less sensitive to idiosyncratic shocks affecting particular country pairs, thereby offering a more stable estimate of the impact of environmental policies. Finally, this approach reduces potential biases related to geopolitical factors or specific trade agreements that affect bilateral relations, thus offering a broader and less context-dependent analysis (Baldwin, 2012). This makes it a useful complement to bilateral trade analyses by providing a more general and synthetic perspective on the trade of environmental goods.

3 Empirical Strategy

In this study, we use the *entropy balancing* method developed by Hainmueller (2012) to estimate the impact of the Kyoto Protocol on the trade of environmental goods. The Kyoto Protocol is treated as the *treatment*, with Annex B countries that ratified the protocol classified as *treated*, and those that did not ratify it or were not subject to binding targets classified as *untreated*. This method addresses potential selection bias, as Annex B countries may have specific characteristics—such as stricter environmental policies or more advanced technologies—that influence both their decision to adopt the

protocol and their trade performance.

The counterfactual framework is based on the comparison of two potential outcomes: Y_1 , the outcome (defined as either exports, imports, or the sum of both for environmental goods as a share of GDP) for a country that ratified the Kyoto Protocol, and Y_0 , the outcome for a country that did not. The causal effect of the treatment—ratifying the Kyoto Protocol—is defined as the difference between these two states for treated countries:

$$ATT = \mathbb{E}[Y_1|T = 1] - \mathbb{E}[Y_0|T = 1]$$

where ATT denotes the average treatment effect on the treated. The main challenge is that we never observe Y_0 for countries that ratified the protocol. To address this, we use the untreated countries as a control group, applying weights such that their pre-treatment characteristics become comparable to those of the treated group.

Entropy balancing consists in computing weights w_i for untreated countries ($T=0$) so that the average of the pre-treatment covariates \mathbf{X} in the control group exactly matches that of the treated group:

$$\sum_{i:T=0} w_i \mathbf{X}_i = \sum_{i:T=1} \mathbf{X}_i$$

The weights w_i are obtained by minimizing a distance function based on entropy under the following constraint:

$$\min_w \sum_{i:T=0} w_i \log(w_i)$$

subject to:

$$\sum_{i:T=0} w_i = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i:T=0} w_i \mathbf{X}_i = \bar{\mathbf{X}}_T$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{X}}_T$ denotes the mean of covariates in the treated group. Once these weights are obtained, we use them in a linear regression model that includes country and time

fixed effects to control for unobserved heterogeneity and time-varying factors unrelated to treatment:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta T_{it} + \gamma \mathbf{X}_{it} + \lambda_i + \delta_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

where T_{it} is a binary variable equal to 1 if country i is treated in year t , \mathbf{X}_{it} denotes control covariates, λ_i are country fixed effects, and δ_t are time fixed effects. The coefficient β provides an estimate of the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on the trade of environmental goods.

This non-parametric method presents several advantages. Unlike *propensity score matching* or *difference-in-differences* approaches, entropy balancing does not require specifying a functional form for the outcome equation or the treatment assignment mechanism, thus reducing the risk of model misspecification. It also ensures exact covariate balance between treated and control groups, even in small samples or when few untreated units are available. Furthermore, the method enables the construction of a synthetic control group that accurately represents the counterfactual scenario for Annex B countries, thereby enhancing the robustness of the results.³

4 Data

Subsection 4.1 describes the main variables used in this study. Subsection 4.2 provides descriptive statistics.

4.1 Variable Description

This study analyzes how the entry into force of the Kyoto Protocol affected environmental goods trade among Annex B countries from 1997 to 2021. The key explanatory variable, *kyoto*, is a binary indicator equal to 1 from 2005 (the year the Kyoto Protocol entered into force) for Annex B countries, and 0 otherwise (see Table 10 for the list of

³One limitation of this method is that it assumes no unobserved confounding variables and can produce extreme weights in the presence of large imbalances. In our study, these risks are mitigated by strong covariate overlap and careful calibration of the specification.

countries). This variable is designed to capture the direct effect of the Kyoto Protocol’s implementation on environmental goods trade, thus enabling an evaluation of how international climate commitments influence trade patterns. This approach is consistent with prior studies that also use the official entry-into-force date as a critical threshold for analysis (Almer and Winkler, 2017; Aichele and Felbermayr, 2015a).

Data on environmental goods trade are sourced from the Comtrade (2018) database. Trade values are expressed as a percentage of GDP to normalize flows relative to the size of each economy, thereby allowing consistent cross-country comparisons. Environmental goods are defined according to OECD and Eurostat classifications⁴ and are aggregated at the six-digit level of the Harmonized System (HS). Total trade data, including imports and exports, are drawn from the IMF Direction of Trade Statistics⁵.

In addition to the main variable of interest, several control variables are included to better explain the dynamics of environmental goods trade. Their inclusion helps to reduce omitted variable bias and improve the robustness of the results:

- *Growth*: The GDP growth rate is essential for capturing the effect of economic conditions on the trade of environmental goods. Rapid economic growth tends to increase energy consumption, which may in turn stimulate demand for green technologies (Zhang et al., 2016).
- *GDP per capita*: The logarithm of GDP per capita is used as a proxy for the level of economic development. Wealthier countries are generally more inclined to adopt environmental technologies, as they possess the financial capacity to invest in ecological solutions. This variable thus controls for the influence of development level on environmental goods trade.
- *Rents*: Natural resource rents, measured as a percentage of GDP, capture the share of national income derived from the exploitation of natural resources (such as oil, gas, minerals, etc.). A country that derives a substantial portion of its revenues from natural resources may face a “green constraint”: growing domestic and international pressure to reduce its environmental footprint could lead to

⁴OECD and Eurostat, *The Environmental Goods & Services Industry: Manual for Data Collection and Analysis, 1999*

⁵https://climatedata.imf.org/datasets/8636ce866c8a404b8d9baeaffa2c6cb3_0/about

increased investment in environmental technologies, such as renewable energy or pollution control systems, in an effort to diversify the economy and reduce fossil fuel dependency.

- *CO₂ per capita*: The logarithm of CO₂ emissions per capita is included to account for a country's environmental pressure and its potential effect on environmental goods trade. Countries with high emission levels may have stronger incentives to import technologies aimed at reducing emissions, such as renewables or waste management solutions.
- *Manufacturing*: This variable measures the share of manufacturing value added in GDP. A large manufacturing sector may affect the trade of environmental goods, as manufacturing industries are often major users of these technologies—whether for improving energy efficiency or for reducing polluting emissions.
- *Corruption*: This is a measure of institutional quality. Based on an index from the International Country Risk Guide (ICRG) database, it is included to account for the impact of institutions on the trade of environmental goods. Strong institutions that ensure enforcement of environmental laws and facilitate market access can support the trade of such goods. Countries with higher institutional quality are therefore more likely to respond positively to international commitments like the Kyoto Protocol and to adopt green technologies more rapidly.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Figure 1 presents a comparison of the average level of environmental goods trade based on countries' commitment status under the Kyoto Protocol. The graph reveals a marked difference between Annex B countries and others, both in terms of exports and imports of environmental goods.

Regarding *exports*, Annex B countries exhibit a higher level of environmental goods exports compared to non-Annex B countries. This disparity may be explained by a stronger motivation among Annex B countries to promote environmentally friendly technologies and products, driven by the emission reduction targets imposed by the Protocol.

Figure 1: Average level of environmental goods trade by Kyoto commitment status

As for *imports*, Annex B countries also show significantly higher levels of environmental goods imports. This trend could be attributed to stronger domestic demand for goods that support sustainable practices, reflecting their international commitments to reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

Figure 2 illustrates the evolution of environmental goods trade from 1997 to 2021. The trade of these goods began to rise in the early 2000s, followed by a period of rapid growth. This trend can be attributed to various factors, including growing environmental pressures and a gradual shift toward more sustainable commercial and governmental strategies in the long run.

5 Main Results

The analysis presented in Table 1 highlights the impact of the Kyoto Protocol on total trade, imports, and exports of environmental goods, with a particular focus on industrialized countries listed in Annex B.

Table 1: Kyoto Protocol Effect

Dependent variable	Total Trade			Total Importations			Total Exportations		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Kyoto	0.986*** (0.156)	0.986*** (0.156)	0.988*** (0.155)	0.710*** (0.118)	0.710*** (0.118)	0.710*** (0.118)	0.285*** (0.107)	0.286*** (0.107)	0.287*** (0.107)
Growth	0.030** (0.012)	0.031** (0.012)	0.031** (0.012)	0.033*** (0.007)	0.033*** (0.007)	0.033*** (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)
GDP per capita	0.495 (0.469)	0.506 (0.471)	0.466 (0.470)	-1.269*** (0.286)	-1.265*** (0.287)	-1.272*** (0.287)	1.793*** (0.294)	1.800*** (0.295)	1.770*** (0.294)
CO2 per capita	0.207 (0.264)	0.223 (0.265)	0.212 (0.265)	0.288* (0.167)	0.293* (0.167)	0.288* (0.167)	-0.127 (0.163)	-0.116 (0.163)	-0.122 (0.164)
Rents	-0.054*** (0.015)	-0.053*** (0.015)	-0.054*** (0.015)	-0.047*** (0.010)	-0.047*** (0.010)	-0.048*** (0.010)	-0.007 (0.010)	-0.007 (0.010)	-0.008 (0.010)
Manufacturing	0.135*** (0.032)	0.134*** (0.032)	0.134*** (0.032)	0.070*** (0.016)	0.070*** (0.016)	0.070*** (0.016)	0.066*** (0.019)	0.065*** (0.019)	0.065*** (0.019)
Corruption	-0.152* (0.078)	-0.148* (0.078)	-0.150* (0.078)	0.020 (0.044)	0.021 (0.045)	0.020 (0.044)	-0.155*** (0.055)	-0.153*** (0.055)	-0.154*** (0.055)
Observations	2502	2502	2502	2510	2510	2510	2507	2507	2507
R square	.9491	.9491	.9492	.9353	.9354	.9353	.9306	.9307	.9307
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes								
Trend	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Regional trend	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

Notes: We report the results on the impact of the Kyoto Protocol on trade in environmental goods. The results for total trade, imports, and exports are reported in columns [1] to [3], [4] to [6], and [7] to [9], respectively. We test the robustness of our main findings by controlling for country-specific and regional trends. The constant is included in the estimations, but not reported in the table. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$.

Figure 2: Evolution of total environmental goods trade

5.1 Overall Effect on Environmental Goods Trade

Overall, the entry into force of the Kyoto Protocol is associated with a significant increase in the trade of environmental goods. The coefficients associated with the *Kyoto* variable in Table 1 are positive, indicating that the agreement encouraged a rise in trade within this sector. For total trade, the estimated effects range between 0.986 and 0.988 percentage points. Given that the average share of environmental goods trade in our sample is 3.31%, this corresponds to an increase of approximately 29.8%. This finding aligns with the work of [Costantini and Crespi \(2010c\)](#), who demonstrate that strict environmental regulations stimulate trade in green technologies. Similarly, [Sauvage \(2014\)](#) highlight that rigorous environmental policies significantly increase the global export share of environmental goods.

The Kyoto Protocol, therefore, provided strong incentives for industrialized countries to shift toward green technologies, thereby boosting environmental goods trade. However, the observed patterns suggest that these countries primarily sought to meet their own domestic demand.

5.2 Import Dynamics

The most pronounced impact of the Kyoto Protocol is observed in the imports of environmental goods. In columns (4), (5), and (6) of Table 1, the coefficients related to imports are statistically significant and hover around 0.710. This implies that industrialized countries experienced an increase in imports of approximately 0.76 to 0.86 percentage points relative to other countries, which corresponds to an increase of about 36,7% to 41,6% compared to the average of our sample. . Several factors help explain this trend. On the one hand, the need to comply with emission reduction requirements generated increased demand for green technologies. On the other hand, despite their technological capabilities, some developed countries were unable to produce enough of the goods required for their ecological transition, prompting them to import sophisticated equipment or technologies not yet domestically available.

[De Melo and Solleder \(2020\)](#) support this view by showing that, despite having internal production capacity, developed countries continue to import environmental goods due to trade barriers and technological specialization. Moreover, the increase in imports also reflects a desire to diversify sources of supply and modernize industrial infrastructure quickly, in line with the targets set by the Kyoto Protocol.

5.3 Effect on Exports

Regarding exports, the effect of Kyoto entry into force is more modest. In columns (7), (8), and (9), the coefficients range between 0.285 and 0.287, corresponding to an increase of approximately 23% compared to the average of our sample. This limited growth can be explained by the fact that a large share of green technology production was likely allocated to meeting domestic demand, driven by the modernization objectives imposed by Kyoto. Additionally, strong international competition in the environmental technology sector may have constrained export opportunities. According to [Wang et al. \(2013\)](#), while some industries benefit in the long term from strict regulation, others may incur short-term losses.

Annex B countries likely devoted significant resources to research, development, and industrial adaptation in order to meet their emissions reduction targets, as noted by

Porter and Van der Linde (1995). This reallocation of resources may have temporarily limited their ability to export green technologies at scale.

Furthermore, technologically advanced countries that did not ratify the Protocol—such as the United States or China (non-Annex B)—continued to play a major role in the global export of environmental goods. Their dominance reduced the available market share for Kyoto signatories. As shown by Bacchetta et al. (2019), although the liberalization of environmental goods trade contributes to lowering global emissions, the growth in exports remains relatively moderate.

6 Heterogeneity

In this section, we further explore the heterogeneity of the Kyoto Protocol’s effects on the trade of environmental goods. We distinguish between two main dimensions. First, we examine how the economic and environmental characteristics of Annex B countries influence the intensity of the estimated effect. Subsection 6.1 investigates the role of technological innovation through the share of environmental patents. Subsection 6.2 considers the size of the economy, while subsection 6.3 focuses on the importance of the manufacturing sector. Lastly, subsection 6.4 analyzes the role of overall environmental performance in shaping the effect of the Protocol. Second, we investigate institutional and geopolitical dimensions. Subsection 6.5 examines the differences between EU and non-EU countries, in order to assess the role of regional integration in the effectiveness of climate policy. Subsection 6.6 focuses on the influence of the Paris Agreement, testing the hypothesis that it amplified the trade dynamics initiated under Kyoto.⁶

6.1 Environmental Technologies

In this section, we examine how the level of technological development in the environmental domain influences the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on environmental goods trade. To do this, we use the ratio of patents related to environmental technologies to the total

⁶The graphs illustrate the evolution of the Kyoto Protocol’s effect across each heterogeneity variable. The effect is statistically significant when the curve rises above the red line. If the red line is absent, this indicates consistent significance across the entire distribution.

number of patents filed across all technologies at the national level (OECD data). The results of this analysis are presented in the first column of Figure 3.

The results show that the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on total environmental goods trade increases significantly with the level of environmental technology. At low levels of environmental patents, the estimated effect is close to zero and statistically insignificant. In contrast, beyond a certain threshold, the confidence interval clearly rises above the reference line, indicating a significant and increasing effect. This suggests that only countries with sufficiently advanced technological capabilities are able to convert Kyoto commitments into tangible commercial opportunities. This finding is consistent with [Taguchi and Sato \(2022\)](#), who show that countries combining strict environmental policies with a solid innovation base tend to achieve stronger trade performance in clean technologies.

The effect of the Kyoto Protocol on exports is also positively influenced by the level of environmental technology. The graph displays an upward-sloping trend, with the effect becoming significant in the most technologically advanced countries. This result aligns with the findings of [Jin et al. \(2021\)](#), who demonstrate that environmental innovation, when combined with strict regulation, enhances the export competitiveness of manufacturing firms in China. However, [Dechezleprêtre et al. \(2011\)](#) nuance this relationship by noting that countries leading in patenting do not always dominate export markets for green technologies, due to structural gaps between innovation and industrial deployment capacity.

For imports, the Kyoto Protocol's effect is also significant but much smaller across the distribution, and it increases with the level of environmental technology. The graph shows that even at low levels of environmental technology, the estimated effect is already positive, and the confidence interval remains entirely above zero. This indicates that technologically advanced countries also tend to import more environmental goods.

6.2 Economic Size

We examine here the differentiated effect of the Kyoto Protocol based on the size of the economy, measured by the logarithm of GDP. The results are presented in the second

Figure 3: Heterogeneity in the effect of the Kyoto Protocol

column of Figure 3.

The effect of the Kyoto Protocol on total environmental goods trade appears to increase with economic size. At low levels of GDP, the estimated effect is small and not statistically significant. Beyond a certain threshold, the confidence interval rises above zero and the effect becomes significant, suggesting that larger economies benefit more from Kyoto commitments. This finding supports the results of [Shi and Xu \(2018\)](#), who argue that larger economies are better equipped to absorb regulatory costs while maintaining a comparative advantage due to more developed trade infrastructure and value chains.

For exports, the estimated slope is clearly upward, and the effect becomes significant for countries with the highest GDP levels. This indicates that large economies are more effective at converting environmental commitments into export opportunities, thanks to a more diversified industrial base and greater capacity to develop and produce environmental goods. This result is supported by recent work from [Shi and Xu \(2018\)](#), who find that the positive effects of environmental policies on export performance are more

pronounced in large economies, given their ability to mobilize resources for industrial adaptation.

For imports, the estimated effect remains relatively stable and highly significant across the distribution. This implies that economic size significantly influences the propensity to import environmental goods in response to climate commitments. In other words, larger economies tend to increase their imports of environmental goods compared to the smaller ones following Kyoto implementation.

6.3 Size of the Manufacturing Sector

In this section, we examine how the size of the manufacturing sector—measured by its share in GDP—modulates the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on environmental goods trade. The results are presented in the third column of Figure 3.

For total environmental goods trade, the effect of the Kyoto Protocol is significant but relatively modest across the distribution. The curve remains above zero, with a confidence interval that does not intersect the reference line, indicating an overall positive but moderate effect, regardless of the size of the manufacturing sector. This observation is consistent with [Antonietti et al. \(2015\)](#), who show that while industrial firms can benefit from environmental regulation, the aggregate impact also depends on the country's productive structure.

For exports, a growing effect of the Protocol is observed with increasing manufacturing intensity. The effect is not significant for countries with low manufacturing shares, but becomes more pronounced and statistically significant for those with higher manufacturing sector contributions to GDP. The curve steepens in the upper part of the distribution, suggesting that countries with more developed industrial sectors have benefited more from the Protocol in terms of exporting environmental goods. These results are consistent with [Lechner and Wunsch \(2021\)](#), who show that industrial specialization can enhance the ability of countries to capitalize on strict environmental regulations through exports.

In contrast, for imports, the effect of the Kyoto Protocol is positive and statistically significant, but decreases sharply as manufacturing intensity increases. In other words, as

the manufacturing sector grows, the Protocol’s impact on environmental goods imports diminishes.

6.4 Environmental Performance

The last column of Figure 3 illustrates how environmental performance conditions the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on environmental goods trade. This variable captures a country’s progress in improving environmental health, mitigating climate change, and preserving ecosystem vitality (Block et al., 2024).

For total trade, the effect remains relatively flat and insignificant until environmental performance surpasses a certain threshold. Beyond that, the curve rises above the reference line and the confidence interval no longer includes zero, indicating a positive trade response to the Protocol among the most environmentally committed countries. A similar pattern is observed for exports: the estimated effect strengthens toward the upper end of the distribution, suggesting that the highest-rated countries in environmental performance are also the most capable of translating Kyoto obligations into export opportunities. For imports, the profile is also similar: no significant effect is observed in countries with low environmental performance, while a positive and significant effect emerges among countries with high environmental scores.

These findings are in line with studies such as Verdolini et al. (2016), which emphasize the role of environmental institutions in facilitating the integration of green innovations into international trade, and Damert et al. (2022), who argue that green competitiveness relies partly on the alignment between regulatory ambition and commercial implementation capacity.

6.5 EU Member States vs. Non-EU Countries

In this section, we compare the effect of the Kyoto Protocol on environmental goods trade between two distinct groups: European Union (EU) member states and non-EU countries. This distinction aims to assess whether belonging to a common institutional framework, namely the EU, alters the intensity or nature of the Protocol’s impact. The

Table 2: Heterogeneity: EU member and non-member countries

Dependent variable	Total Trade			Total Importations			Total Exportations		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Kyoto	0.415** (0.166)	0.415** (0.166)	0.416** (0.166)	0.554*** (0.131)	0.554*** (0.131)	0.554*** (0.131)	-0.145 (0.119)	-0.145 (0.119)	-0.144 (0.120)
EU	-0.291 (0.196)	-0.291 (0.196)	-0.291 (0.195)	-0.015 (0.137)	-0.015 (0.137)	-0.015 (0.137)	-0.291*** (0.087)	-0.291*** (0.087)	-0.291*** (0.087)
Kyoto_EU	1.007*** (0.114)	1.007*** (0.114)	1.010*** (0.114)	0.343*** (0.062)	0.343*** (0.062)	0.343*** (0.063)	0.685*** (0.072)	0.685*** (0.072)	0.687*** (0.073)
Growth	0.035** (0.014)	0.035** (0.014)	0.036** (0.014)	0.034*** (0.009)	0.034*** (0.009)	0.034*** (0.009)	0.002 (0.009)	0.002 (0.009)	0.002 (0.009)
GDP per capita	0.500 (0.525)	0.500 (0.525)	0.515 (0.526)	-1.295*** (0.308)	-1.295*** (0.308)	-1.290*** (0.308)	1.823*** (0.322)	1.823*** (0.322)	1.833*** (0.324)
CO2 per capita	0.350 (0.292)	0.350 (0.292)	0.351 (0.292)	0.271 (0.177)	0.271 (0.177)	0.271 (0.177)	0.035 (0.172)	0.035 (0.172)	0.035 (0.172)
Rents	-0.048** (0.022)	-0.048** (0.022)	-0.049** (0.022)	-0.051*** (0.016)	-0.051*** (0.016)	-0.052*** (0.016)	0.002 (0.014)	0.002 (0.014)	0.001 (0.014)
Manufacturing	0.133*** (0.038)	0.133*** (0.038)	0.134*** (0.037)	0.074*** (0.018)	0.074*** (0.018)	0.074*** (0.018)	0.060*** (0.022)	0.060*** (0.022)	0.061*** (0.022)
Corruption	-0.198** (0.083)	-0.198** (0.083)	-0.198** (0.083)	0.016 (0.047)	0.016 (0.047)	0.016 (0.047)	-0.197*** (0.058)	-0.197*** (0.058)	-0.197*** (0.058)
Observations	1705	1705	1705	1710	1710	1710	1706	1706	1706
R square	.9527	.9527	.9527	.9406	.9406	.9406	.935	.935	.9351
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Trend	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Regional trend	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

Notes: The results for total trade, imports, and exports are presented in columns [1] to [3], [4] to [6], and [7] to [9], respectively. The constant is included in the estimations but not reported in the table. * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

European Union represents an integrated economic area characterized by coordinated environmental policies, harmonized regulations, and a single market that facilitates the circulation of goods and technologies.

The results, presented in Table 2, reveal significant differences between the two groups. The effect of the Kyoto Protocol on total environmental goods trade is statistically significant across the full sample, but it is notably stronger for EU member states. Regarding exports, EU member states show a marked increase in outbound flows of environmental goods. This reflects the capacity of European firms to innovate and comply with new standards while remaining competitive in international markets. This suggests that the EU has enabled the adoption of ambitious environmental policies without undermining the competitiveness of its members. European firms appear to have capitalized on regulatory constraints to improve their performance, notably through the adoption of cleaner and more exportable technologies. In contrast, the impact on imports is more modest but still positive, indicating that EU countries continue to complement their domestic production by importing green technologies, possibly due to a desire to diversify supply sources or access specialized equipment.

These findings highlight the structuring role of supranational institutions in the implementation of multilateral environmental agreements. The European Union, as an integrated economic entity, appears to have helped its members absorb the constraints imposed by the Kyoto Protocol more effectively. The presence of harmonized environmental policies, combined with support mechanisms for green innovation, likely reduced adjustment costs for European firms, thereby supporting the expansion of environmental trade—particularly through exports.

Finally, these differences suggest that the effects of climate agreements depend not only on formal entry into force, but also on the institutional capacity to implement them. Membership in a regional entity such as the EU provides an additional lever to translate environmental commitments into concrete trade dynamics. This interaction between regional governance and international regulation is a key factor in understanding the divergent trajectories observed in environmental trade.

6.6 The Paris Agreement as a Catalyst

This section examines the extent to which the articulation between the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement⁷ has influenced trade in environmental goods. The goal is to assess whether the entry into force of the Paris Agreement—building upon the commitments already initiated under Kyoto—further intensified trade flows, particularly by strengthening the export capacity of industrialized countries (Annex B). The analysis relies on an interaction variable between the two international agreements. The variable *Paris* is a binary indicator equal to 1 from 2016 onward, while the variable *Kyoto* takes the value 1 starting in 2005. The interaction term $Kyoto \times Paris$ is thus constructed as the product of these two variables and equals 1 only during the 2016–2021 period, corresponding to the post-Paris years, but within a policy context already shaped by the Kyoto Protocol.

The results, presented in table 3, reveal a positive and significant effect of this interaction on total trade, imports, and exports of environmental goods. This suggests that the Paris Agreement not only reinforced demand (through imports) but also stimulated domestic supply and technological innovation, allowing countries to upgrade their production and become more actively integrated into global green value chains.

The coefficients associated with the Kyoto Protocol alone show a significant and positive impact on total trade and imports, but no significant effect on exports. This indicates that, initially, Annex B countries primarily responded to their climate commitments by importing environmental technologies. This finding is consistent with Dekker et al. (2012), who highlight the early reliance on imports during initial phases of environmental regulation, and with Popp (2011), who emphasize the time lag between regulatory-driven green innovation and its translation into commercial gains.

The interaction effect between Kyoto and Paris proves to be strongly significant across all trade dimensions. This result suggests that Annex B countries have gradually developed productive and innovative capabilities, enabling them not only to import but also to export green technologies. The Paris Agreement appears to have acted as a catalyst by establishing a more incentive-based governance framework, thereby enhancing

⁷Adopted in 2015, the Paris Agreement commits countries to limit global warming to below 2°C through nationally determined contributions (NDCs).

Table 3: Effect of the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement

Dependent variable	Total Trade			Total Importations			Total Exportations		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Kyoto	0.440*** (0.151)	0.442*** (0.151)	0.443*** (0.151)	0.427*** (0.117)	0.427*** (0.117)	0.428*** (0.117)	0.025 (0.103)	0.027 (0.103)	0.027 (0.103)
Kyoto_Paris	1.600*** (0.183)	1.595*** (0.184)	1.598*** (0.183)	0.829*** (0.112)	0.829*** (0.113)	0.829*** (0.112)	0.763*** (0.113)	0.759*** (0.113)	0.762*** (0.113)
Growth	0.010 (0.011)	0.010 (0.011)	0.010 (0.011)	0.022*** (0.007)	0.022*** (0.007)	0.022*** (0.007)	-0.012* (0.007)	-0.012 (0.007)	-0.012 (0.007)
GDP per capita	0.803* (0.426)	0.806* (0.427)	0.799* (0.425)	-1.109*** (0.252)	-1.109*** (0.252)	-1.109*** (0.252)	1.938*** (0.293)	1.941*** (0.294)	1.936*** (0.293)
CO2 per capita	0.618** (0.241)	0.622** (0.241)	0.620*** (0.240)	0.499*** (0.153)	0.499*** (0.153)	0.499*** (0.153)	0.069 (0.161)	0.073 (0.161)	0.071 (0.161)
Rents	-0.060*** (0.016)	-0.060*** (0.016)	-0.060*** (0.016)	-0.051*** (0.010)	-0.051*** (0.010)	-0.051*** (0.010)	-0.010 (0.011)	-0.010 (0.011)	-0.010 (0.011)
Manufacturing	0.117*** (0.032)	0.117*** (0.032)	0.117*** (0.032)	0.061*** (0.015)	0.061*** (0.015)	0.061*** (0.015)	0.057*** (0.019)	0.057*** (0.019)	0.058*** (0.019)
Corruption	-0.180** (0.074)	-0.178** (0.074)	-0.178** (0.074)	0.006 (0.043)	0.006 (0.043)	0.006 (0.043)	-0.169*** (0.053)	-0.168*** (0.053)	-0.168*** (0.053)
Observations	2502	2502	2502	2510	2510	2510	2507	2507	2507
R square	.9544	.9544	.9544	.9414	.9414	.9414	.9345	.9345	.9346
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes								
Trend	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Regional trend	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

Notes: The results for total trade, imports, and exports are presented in columns [1] to [3], [4] to [6], and [7] to [9], respectively. The constant is included in the estimations but not reported in the table. * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

green industrial competitiveness. This dynamic echoes the “Porter hypothesis,” which posits that ambitious environmental policies can stimulate innovation and economic performance (Porter and Van der Linde, 1995). It is also supported by recent empirical studies such as Jin et al. (2021) and Taguchi and Sato (2022), which show that stringent environmental regulations can yield positive export competitiveness effects in green sectors. These results underscore the importance of the continuity of international commitments in fostering a durable structural transformation of environmental trade.

7 Transmission Channel

This section investigates the role of renewable energy consumption (% of total final energy consumption) as a transmission mechanism through which the Kyoto Protocol may have contributed to the growth in environmental goods trade. The central hypothesis is that commitments under the Kyoto Protocol incentivized signatory countries to increase their use of renewable energy sources, which in turn stimulated demand for environmental technologies. This dynamic would then manifest as an intensification of trade in these goods. The results are presented in Table 4.

To test this hypothesis, we follow a two-step empirical strategy. First (column 1), we examine whether the entry into force of the Kyoto Protocol is associated with a significant increase in renewable energy consumption among Annex B countries. The results indicate that Annex B countries did, in fact, increase the share of renewables in their energy mix, all else being equal. In the second step (column 2), we assess the effect of this increased renewable energy consumption on environmental goods trade. The estimates reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship: greater use of renewable energy is associated with higher levels of environmental goods trade. This finding highlights a direct link between the energy transition and trade dynamics. Investments in renewable energy infrastructure—such as solar panels, wind turbines, smart grids, and related technologies—require the acquisition of high-tech goods, which are often imported or traded among specialized commercial partners.

These results enrich our understanding of the economic effects of international climate policy. By fostering the adoption of clean energy, the Kyoto Protocol has contributed

to the expansion of environmental goods trade. This interpretation is consistent with the conclusions of [Costantini and Crespi \(2010b\)](#), who emphasize that well-designed climate policies can shift countries' technological and trade trajectories by reinforcing the interaction between energy policy, innovation, and trade openness.

Table 4: Transmission channel: Percentage of renewable energy consumption

Variable dépendante	(Renewable Energy Conso.)	(Total Trade)
Kyoto	3.196*** (0.401)	
Renewable Energy Conso.		0.032*** (0.006)
Growth	0.005 (0.029)	0.022*** (0.006)
GDP per capita	1.972** (0.912)	0.091 (0.227)
CO2 per capita	-15.697*** (0.774)	0.114 (0.182)
Rents	0.122* (0.064)	-0.002 (0.006)
Manufacturing	0.274*** (0.049)	0.073*** (0.011)
Corruption	0.512** (0.236)	-0.128** (0.056)
Observations	2586	2501
R square	.9829	.9012
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes

8 Robustness Checks

This section focuses on the robustness of our results. First, we employ propensity score matching (subsection [8.1](#)). Then, in subsection [8.2](#), we introduce additional control variables into our baseline model. Finally, we exclude top environmental goods exporters from the sample (subsection [8.3](#)).

8.1 Propensity Score Matching (PSM)

In this part of the analysis, we use Propensity Score Matching (PSM) as a robustness check. PSM is a quasi-experimental method that uses a propensity score to construct an

artificial control group by matching each treated unit with a non-treated unit that has similar observable characteristics. The propensity score represents the probability that a country receives the treatment (i.e., ratifies the Kyoto Protocol). The key assumption is that treatment assignment is random conditional on observable variables—meaning that, beyond these variables, there are no unobserved factors influencing both potential outcomes and treatment. In the case of the ATT, this conditional independence assumption can be written as: $Y_0 \perp T|X$.

The results presented in Table 5 show that the magnitude and direction of the estimated coefficients remain consistent and statistically significant across all matching methods (the nearest neighbors, radius, local regression, and kernel). Nearest neighbor matching (1-to-1, 1-to-2, 1-to-3) pairs each treated unit with the closest one, two, or three control units based on propensity scores. Radius matching selects all control units within a specified distance (radius) from the treated unit’s score, allowing for variable numbers of matches. Local regression and kernel matching use weighted averages of control units, assigning higher weights to those with scores closer to the treated unit, thus capturing more information and smoothing differences across the distribution. For total environmental goods trade, the ATT coefficients range from 0.8080 to 1.0858, indicating a positive and significant effect of Kyoto Protocol entry into force. Similarly, for environmental goods imports, the coefficients lie between 0.2974 and 0.3962 and remain significant, confirming a substantial increase in imports following entry into force. With regard to environmental goods exports, the results also indicate a robust effect, with coefficients ranging from 0.5181 to 0.6683, all significant at the 1% or 5% level. The consistency of the coefficients across different matching methods confirms the robustness of our initial findings and reinforces the conclusion that the Kyoto Protocol had a positive impact on environmental goods trade.

8.2 Additional Variables

For this robustness check, we introduce three additional variables: the KOF Globalization Index (*Globalization Index*), energy intensity (*Energy*), and the level of education (*Education*). These variables are included to capture structural dimensions of inter-

Table 5: PSM Robustness Results

Dependent Variable	Nearest Neighbor Matching			Radius Matching			Other Methods	
	1-Nearest	2-Nearest	3-Nearest	r=0.001	r=0.01	r=0.05	Local Linear	Kernel
Total Environmental Goods	1.0858** (0.4784)	1.0263*** (0.3742)	1.0325*** (0.3903)	1.0841*** (0.3633)	1.0214*** (0.2895)	0.9116*** (0.2892)	0.9047*** (0.2268)	0.8080*** (0.2649)
Observations	2502	2502	2502	2502	2502	2502	2502	2502
Treated	524	524	524	524	524	524	524	524
Control	1978	1978	1978	1978	1978	1978	1978	1978
Pseudo R²	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950	0.3950
Imports of Environmental Goods	0.3553 (0.2548)	0.3369* (0.1968)	0.3962* (0.2026)	0.3962** (0.1566)	0.3827** (0.1695)	0.3409** (0.1652)	0.3390** (0.1433)	0.2974** (0.1350)
Observations	2690	2690	2690	2690	2690	2690	2690	2690
Treated	524	524	524	524	524	524	524	524
Control	2166	2166	2166	2166	2166	2166	2166	2166
Pseudo R²	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952	0.2952
Exports of Environmental Goods	0.6458*** (0.2064)	0.6217*** (0.1928)	0.6753*** (0.2180)	0.6683*** (0.1264)	0.6484*** (0.1643)	0.5753*** (0.1611)	0.5707*** (0.1373)	0.5181*** (0.1409)
Observations	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684	2684
Treated	524	524	524	524	524	524	524	524
Control	2160	2160	2160	2160	2160	2160	2160	2160
Pseudo R²	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676	0.4676

national trade and environmental policy that may influence the flow of environmental goods. The detailed results are presented in Table 6.

The inclusion of the KOF Globalization Index aims to measure the degree of economic, social, and political openness of each country. As highlighted in the literature, greater integration into the global economy is associated with intensified trade flows, notably by facilitating the diffusion of green technologies, environmental cooperation, and the exchange of complex goods (Dreher, 2006; Bergh et al., 2017). Our findings confirm this effect. The globalization index has a positive and statistically significant impact on total trade—especially imports, and to a lesser extent exports—of environmental goods. This suggests that greater international openness enhances trade in these products, likely through mechanisms such as learning effects, regulatory harmonization, or technology transfer.

The variable *Energy* reflects the amount of energy used to produce one unit of economic output. A lower ratio indicates greater energy efficiency. This is a key factor for understanding the interaction between energy consumption and trade dynamics. The significant and negative impact of *Energy* in most regressions confirms that more energy-intensive economies tend to underperform in international trade in environmental goods. This supports the findings of Kander et al. (2017) and Doe and Smith (2016), who show

Table 6: Robustesse: Variables additionnelles

Dependent variable	Total Trade												Total Importations												Total Exportations																							
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)												
Kyoto	1.195*** (0.161)	0.820*** (0.175)	0.861*** (0.138)	0.852*** (0.161)	0.834*** (0.117)	0.564*** (0.137)	0.374*** (0.076)	0.321*** (0.086)	0.374*** (0.121)	0.256*** (0.118)	0.499*** (0.085)	0.531*** (0.104)	1.195*** (0.161)	0.820*** (0.175)	0.861*** (0.138)	0.852*** (0.161)	0.834*** (0.117)	0.564*** (0.137)	0.374*** (0.076)	0.321*** (0.086)	0.374*** (0.121)	0.256*** (0.118)	0.499*** (0.085)	0.531*** (0.104)	1.195*** (0.161)	0.820*** (0.175)	0.861*** (0.138)	0.852*** (0.161)	0.834*** (0.117)	0.564*** (0.137)	0.374*** (0.076)	0.321*** (0.086)	0.374*** (0.121)	0.256*** (0.118)	0.499*** (0.085)	0.531*** (0.104)												
Growth	0.035*** (0.012)	0.029** (0.012)	0.021 (0.015)	0.025* (0.014)	0.036*** (0.007)	0.033*** (0.007)	0.026*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.007)	-0.001 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.007)	-0.003 (0.009)	-0.003 (0.008)	0.035*** (0.012)	0.029** (0.012)	0.021 (0.015)	0.025* (0.014)	0.036*** (0.007)	0.033*** (0.007)	0.026*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.007)	-0.001 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.007)	-0.003 (0.009)	-0.003 (0.008)	0.035*** (0.012)	0.029** (0.012)	0.021 (0.015)	0.025* (0.014)	0.036*** (0.007)	0.033*** (0.007)	0.026*** (0.008)	0.028*** (0.007)	-0.001 (0.007)	-0.004 (0.007)	-0.003 (0.009)	-0.003 (0.008)												
GDP per capita	0.015 (0.477)	-0.789 (0.518)	1.373*** (0.491)	-0.459 (0.515)	-1.549*** (0.290)	-1.850*** (0.349)	-0.358 (0.241)	-1.135*** (0.269)	1.590*** (0.313)	1.060*** (0.305)	1.767*** (0.309)	0.676** (0.317)	0.015 (0.477)	-0.789 (0.518)	1.373*** (0.491)	-0.459 (0.515)	-1.549*** (0.290)	-1.850*** (0.349)	-0.358 (0.241)	-1.135*** (0.269)	1.590*** (0.313)	1.060*** (0.305)	1.767*** (0.309)	0.676** (0.317)	0.015 (0.477)	-0.789 (0.518)	1.373*** (0.491)	-0.459 (0.515)	-1.549*** (0.290)	-1.850*** (0.349)	-0.358 (0.241)	-1.135*** (0.269)	1.590*** (0.313)	1.060*** (0.305)	1.767*** (0.309)	0.676** (0.317)												
CO2 per capita	-0.092 (0.282)	0.811*** (0.260)	0.738** (0.303)	1.327*** (0.311)	0.125 (0.169)	0.544** (0.185)	0.384** (0.157)	0.677*** (0.172)	-0.270 (0.170)	0.266* (0.160)	0.336* (0.180)	0.649*** (0.178)	-0.092 (0.282)	0.811*** (0.260)	0.738** (0.303)	1.327*** (0.311)	0.125 (0.169)	0.544** (0.185)	0.384** (0.157)	0.677*** (0.172)	-0.270 (0.170)	0.266* (0.160)	0.336* (0.180)	0.649*** (0.178)	-0.092 (0.282)	0.811*** (0.260)	0.738** (0.303)	1.327*** (0.311)	0.125 (0.169)	0.544** (0.185)	0.384** (0.157)	0.677*** (0.172)	-0.270 (0.170)	0.266* (0.160)	0.336* (0.180)	0.649*** (0.178)												
Rents	-0.046*** (0.014)	-0.030** (0.015)	-0.034* (0.019)	-0.002 (0.018)	-0.043*** (0.010)	-0.042*** (0.011)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.027** (0.012)	0.004 (0.009)	0.012 (0.009)	0.004 (0.013)	0.024** (0.011)	-0.046*** (0.014)	-0.030** (0.015)	-0.034* (0.019)	-0.002 (0.018)	-0.043*** (0.010)	-0.042*** (0.011)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.027** (0.012)	0.004 (0.009)	0.012 (0.009)	0.004 (0.013)	0.024** (0.011)	-0.046*** (0.014)	-0.030** (0.015)	-0.034* (0.019)	-0.002 (0.018)	-0.043*** (0.010)	-0.042*** (0.011)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.027** (0.012)	0.004 (0.009)	0.012 (0.009)	0.004 (0.013)	0.024** (0.011)												
Manufacturing	0.146*** (0.031)	0.126*** (0.031)	0.093*** (0.030)	0.087*** (0.028)	0.074*** (0.015)	0.072*** (0.016)	0.036*** (0.013)	0.029** (0.012)	0.073*** (0.019)	0.054*** (0.017)	0.058*** (0.019)	0.058*** (0.018)	0.146*** (0.031)	0.126*** (0.031)	0.093*** (0.030)	0.087*** (0.028)	0.074*** (0.015)	0.072*** (0.016)	0.036*** (0.013)	0.029** (0.012)	0.073*** (0.019)	0.054*** (0.017)	0.058*** (0.019)	0.058*** (0.018)	0.146*** (0.031)	0.126*** (0.031)	0.093*** (0.030)	0.087*** (0.028)	0.074*** (0.015)	0.072*** (0.016)	0.036*** (0.013)	0.029** (0.012)	0.073*** (0.019)	0.054*** (0.017)	0.058*** (0.019)	0.058*** (0.018)												
Corruption	-0.146* (0.077)	-0.079 (0.085)	-0.191** (0.082)	-0.025 (0.072)	0.020 (0.043)	-0.004 (0.058)	-0.068* (0.035)	-0.048 (0.037)	-0.151*** (0.055)	-0.075 (0.064)	-0.112** (0.056)	0.024 (0.052)	-0.146* (0.077)	-0.079 (0.085)	-0.191** (0.082)	-0.025 (0.072)	0.020 (0.043)	-0.004 (0.058)	-0.068* (0.035)	-0.048 (0.037)	-0.151*** (0.055)	-0.075 (0.064)	-0.112** (0.056)	0.024 (0.052)	-0.146* (0.077)	-0.079 (0.085)	-0.191** (0.082)	-0.025 (0.072)	0.020 (0.043)	-0.004 (0.058)	-0.068* (0.035)	-0.048 (0.037)	-0.151*** (0.055)	-0.075 (0.064)	-0.112** (0.056)	0.024 (0.052)												
Globalization Index	0.114*** (0.020)	-0.328*** (0.067)	-0.021*** (0.004)	0.053*** (0.020)	0.067*** (0.012)	-0.176*** (0.046)	-0.107*** (0.012)	0.012 (0.011)	0.049*** (0.012)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.114*** (0.020)	-0.328*** (0.067)	-0.021*** (0.004)	0.053*** (0.020)	0.067*** (0.012)	-0.176*** (0.046)	-0.107*** (0.012)	0.012 (0.011)	0.049*** (0.012)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.114*** (0.020)	-0.328*** (0.067)	-0.021*** (0.004)	0.053*** (0.020)	0.067*** (0.012)	-0.176*** (0.046)	-0.107*** (0.012)	0.012 (0.011)	0.049*** (0.012)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)	0.041*** (0.013)												
Energy Intensity																																																
Education																																																
Observations	2478	2231	1961	1745	2486	2233	1965	1746	2483	2235	1965	1749	2478	2231	1961	1745	2486	2233	1965	1746	2483	2235	1965	1749	2478	2231	1961	1745	2486	2233	1965	1746	2483	2235	1965	1749	2478	2231	1961	1745	2486	2233	1965	1746	2483	2235	1965	1749
R square	.9521	.9553	.9459	.9558	.9395	.9426	.9418	.9521	.9328	.9389	.9263	.9363	.9521	.9553	.9459	.9558	.9395	.9426	.9418	.9521	.9328	.9389	.9263	.9363	.9521	.9553	.9459	.9558	.9395	.9426	.9418	.9521	.9328	.9389	.9263	.9363	.9521	.9553	.9459	.9558	.9395	.9426	.9418	.9521	.9328	.9389	.9263	.9363
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes		

Notes: The results for total trade, imports, and exports are presented in columns [1] to [4], [5] to [8], and [9] to [12], respectively. We test the robustness of our main results by including additional control variables. The constant is included in the estimations but not reported in the table. * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

that countries with high energy intensity face barriers to exporting sophisticated products due to higher production costs and lower competitiveness in green markets. In contrast, countries that improve their energy efficiency benefit from a comparative advantage in value-added trade (Johnson and Lee, 2020; Lastauskas et al., 2024).

The inclusion of the variable *Education*, measured as the gross secondary school enrollment rate, reveals a significant and negative effect on trade flows in environmental goods. At first glance, this result may seem counterintuitive, as higher levels of education are generally associated with better environmental governance, greater support for sustainability policies, and stronger innovation capacity (Green, 2008; Lozano et al., 2013). However, several explanations may account for this negative correlation. On the one hand, countries with higher education levels may focus more on the domestic production of green technologies, thereby reducing their reliance on imports (De Melo and Solleder, 2014). On the other hand, they may adopt stricter environmental standards, which could restrict exports of certain goods through regulatory or sustainability requirements. It is also possible that the observed effect reflects underlying economic structures, where more educated economies tend to specialize in services or environmental R&D rather than in the physical trade of environmental goods (Larraín et al., 2019).

Finally, the inclusion of these additional variables does not substantially alter our main results, thereby confirming the robustness of our initial conclusions. In particular, the effect of the Kyoto Protocol remains statistically significant and stable across most model specifications.

8.3 Sample modification

In this section, we exclude five countries—the United States, China, Germany, Japan, and Canada—from the sample in order to test the robustness of our results. China, the United States, and Germany are the largest exporters of environmental goods in our dataset, and their weight may exert a disproportionate influence on the overall estimates. Japan and Canada, although initial signatories of the Kyoto Protocol, later withdrew, raising questions about the consistency of their long-term commitment. By

removing these particular cases, we aim to assess whether the observed effects of the Kyoto Protocol reflect a broader trend among Annex B countries, or if they are largely driven by a small number of atypical observations.

The results, presented in Table 7, show that the estimated impact of the Kyoto Protocol remains broadly stable even after these exclusions. The coefficients associated with the *Kyoto* variable remain statistically significant across all specifications, although we observe some variation in magnitude. Columns [1] to [3], which capture the effect on total environmental goods trade, the coefficients remain close to 1. Columns [4] to [6], related to imports, the coefficients are slightly lower but still substantial. Finally, columns [7] to [9], which focus on exports, show a moderate decline in coefficients, while retaining statistical significance at the 10% level.

These results indicate that the previously observed dynamics are not solely driven by the largest exporters or by countries that exited the Protocol. The effect of the Kyoto Protocol on environmental goods trade appears to reflect a broader structural trend shared across a more diverse group of industrialized countries. Moreover, the consistency of results despite the exclusion of influential cases reinforces the robustness of our methodology, particularly in the construction of counterfactuals.

9 Conclusion and Discussion

This study has examined the effects of the Kyoto Protocol on the trade of environmental goods, focusing on Annex B countries. Using entropy balancing, we show that the entry into force of this international agreement led to a significant increase in environmental goods trade, particularly through imports. This effect is especially pronounced among industrialized countries, which initially relied more heavily on imports to meet new environmental requirements due to a temporary lack of domestic technological production capacity. In contrast, the effect on exports remained initially limited, suggesting an industrial adjustment phase.

Our findings also highlight that the Paris Agreement reinforced and extended the effects of the Kyoto Protocol. The interaction effect between the two agreements is

Table 7: Robustesse: Sans USA, Chine, Allemagne, Japon et Canada

Dependent variable	Total Trade			Total Importations			Total Exportations		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
Kyoto	1.006*** (0.176)	1.006*** (0.176)	1.002*** (0.176)	0.800*** (0.131)	0.800*** (0.131)	0.794*** (0.130)	0.218* (0.117)	0.218* (0.117)	0.219* (0.117)
Growth	0.032*** (0.012)	0.033*** (0.012)	0.032** (0.012)	0.035*** (0.007)	0.035*** (0.008)	0.034*** (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)	-0.002 (0.007)
GDP per capita	0.525 (0.467)	0.536 (0.469)	0.520 (0.467)	-1.246*** (0.279)	-1.242*** (0.280)	-1.254*** (0.278)	1.799*** (0.289)	1.806*** (0.290)	1.801*** (0.289)
CO2 per capita	0.326 (0.280)	0.345 (0.282)	0.333 (0.279)	0.379** (0.178)	0.386** (0.178)	0.391** (0.176)	-0.101 (0.171)	-0.090 (0.171)	-0.104 (0.171)
Rents	-0.059*** (0.015)	-0.058*** (0.016)	-0.059*** (0.015)	-0.049*** (0.011)	-0.049*** (0.011)	-0.049*** (0.011)	-0.010 (0.010)	-0.010 (0.010)	-0.010 (0.010)
Manufacturing	0.119*** (0.032)	0.119*** (0.033)	0.119*** (0.033)	0.064*** (0.016)	0.064*** (0.016)	0.064*** (0.016)	0.057*** (0.019)	0.056*** (0.019)	0.057*** (0.019)
Corruption	-0.151* (0.081)	-0.146* (0.081)	-0.149* (0.081)	0.026 (0.047)	0.027 (0.047)	0.028 (0.048)	-0.161*** (0.056)	-0.158*** (0.057)	-0.162*** (0.057)
Observations	2389	2389	2389	2397	2397	2397	2394	2394	2394
R square	.9478	.9479	.9478	.9324	.9325	.9327	.9294	.9295	.9295
Time and Country fixed effects	Yes								
Trend	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No
Regional trend	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes

Notes: The results for total trade, imports, and exports are presented in columns [1] to [3], [4] to [6], and [7] to [9], respectively. The constant is included in the estimations but not reported in the table. * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01.

significant across all trade flows, including exports. This trend supports the idea that the progressive establishment of a more inclusive international framework has enabled countries to develop their industrial bases in green technologies. Consistent with the Porter hypothesis, our results illustrate how stringent environmental regulation, in a context of institutional stability, can stimulate innovation and allow countries to benefit from global environmental trade dynamics.

Overall, our analysis emphasizes that the effects of climate policy on trade are neither immediate nor uniform. They depend on countries' ability to mobilize their productive and technological structures to transform regulatory constraints into competitive advantages. From this perspective, our study confirms that international agreements such as Kyoto and Paris have acted as catalysts for structural transformation—but that their effectiveness largely depends on initial country-specific conditions. These findings reinforce the idea that integrating environmental trade into climate regulatory frameworks is a key lever for the transition to a low-carbon economy.

These results carry several implications for public policy design. First, they underscore that environmental regulatory frameworks should be accompanied by active industrial policies aimed at strengthening production, innovation, and investment capacity in green technologies. Without such complementary measures, regulations risk deepening dependence on imports and limiting potential economic benefits. Second, the study highlights the importance of international cooperation in harmonizing environmental standards and facilitating trade in green goods. The European Union, as an integrated market, illustrates how regulatory harmonization can foster technology diffusion and stimulate intra-regional trade. At the global level, initiatives such as the Environmental Goods Agreement (EGA), negotiated under the auspices of the WTO, could contribute to lowering trade barriers on these goods and accelerating the green transition. Ultimately, stronger coordination between climate, industrial, and trade policies appears essential for reconciling environmental objectives with sustainable economic dynamics.

Bibliography

- Abrell, J., Ndoye, F., and Zachmann, G. (2011). Assessing the impact of the eu ets using firm-level data. *Bruegel Working Paper*.
- Aichele, R. and Felbermayr, G. (2013). Estimating the effects of kyoto on bilateral trade flows using matching econometrics. *The World Economy*, 36(3):303–330.
- Aichele, R. and Felbermayr, G. (2015a). Kyoto and carbon leakage: An empirical analysis of the carbon content of bilateral trade. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 97(1):104–115.
- Aichele, R. and Felbermayr, G. (2015b). Kyoto and carbon leakage: An empirical analysis of the impact of the kyoto protocol on carbon emissions. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 73:1–11.
- Almer, C. and Winkler, R. (2017). Analyzing the effectiveness of international environmental policies: The case of the kyoto protocol. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 82:125–151.
- Anderson, J. E. and Van Wincoop, E. (2003). Gravity with gravitas: A solution to the border puzzle. *American economic review*, 93(1):170–192.
- Antonietti, R., Marzucchi, A., and Montresor, S. (2015). Green technology adoption and the export intensity of manufacturing firms: A firm-level investigation. *Research Policy*, 44(5):1015–1028.
- Antweiler, W., Copeland, B. R., and Taylor, M. S. (2001). Is free trade good for the environment? *American economic review*, 91(4):877–908.
- Babiker, M. H., Reilly, J. M., and Jacoby, H. D. (2000). The kyoto protocol and developing countries. *Energy Policy*, 28(9):525–536.
- Bacchetta, M., Bekkers, E., Solleder, J.-M., and Tresa, E. (2019). Trade liberalization of environmental goods and environmental technologies: A potential game changer for climate action? *WTO Working Papers*.

- Baldwin, R. (2012). Trade and industrialisation after globalisation's 2nd unbundling: How building and joining a supply chain are different and why it matters. *Globalization in an age of crisis: Multilateral economic cooperation in the twenty-first century*, pages 165–212.
- Balineau, G. and Melo, J. D. (2013). Do wto trade agreements provide environmental protection? *World Development*, 46:108–122.
- Bergh, A., Nilsson, T., and Waldenström, D. (2017). Globalization and the environmental kuznets curve: A panel data analysis of co2 emissions. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 19(3):369–388.
- Berman, E. and Bui, L. T. M. (2001). Environmental regulation and productivity: Evidence from oil refineries. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 83(3):498–510.
- Block, S., Emerson, J. W., Esty, D. C., de Sherbinin, A., Wendling, Z. A., et al. (2024). 2024 environmental performance index. Technical report, Yale Center for Environmental Law & Policy, New Haven, CT.
- Böhringer, C. and Vogt, C. (2003). Economic and environmental impacts of the kyoto protocol. *The Energy Journal*, 24(3):53–77.
- Bovenberg, A. L. and Smulders, S. (1995). Environmental quality and pollution-augmenting technological change in a two-sector endogenous growth model. *Journal of Public Economics*, 57(3):369–391.
- Cantore, N. and Cheng, C. F. C. (2018). International trade of environmental goods in gravity models. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 226:111–119.
- Comtrade, U. (2018). Gross import, international trade statistics database.
- Copeland, B. R. and Taylor, M. S. (2003). *Trade and the Environment: Theory and Evidence*. Princeton University Press.
- Costantini, V. and Crespi, F. (2008). Environmental regulation and the export dynamics of energy technologies. *Ecological economics*, 66(2-3):447–460.

- Costantini, V. and Crespi, F. (2010a). The environmental kuznets curve in the new millennium. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 12(2):133–157.
- Costantini, V. and Crespi, F. (2010b). Environmental regulation and the export dynamics of energy technologies. *Ecological Economics*, 69(8):1625–1638.
- Costantini, V. and Crespi, F. (2010c). Environmental regulation and trade in energy technologies: Evidence from the eu. *Energy Policy*, 38(8):4788–4796.
- Dai, Z., Zhang, Y., and Zhang, R. (2017). Environmental regulations and trade of environmental goods in apec and oecd countries. *Sustainability*, 9(5):871.
- Damert, M., Rudolph, S., and Arlinghaus, J. (2022). Climate policies and international competitiveness: A review of empirical studies. *Energy Economics*, 112:106137.
- De Melo, J. and Solleder, J.-M. (2014). Determinants of green technology exports: An empirical analysis. *The World Economy*, 37(9):1127–1155.
- De Melo, J. and Solleder, J.-M. (2020). Barriers to trade in environmental goods: How important they are and what should developing countries expect from their removal. *World Development*, 130:104910.
- Dechezleprêtre, A., Glachant, M., and Meniere, Y. (2011). Invention and transfer of climate change mitigation technologies: A global analysis. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 5(1):109–130.
- Dechezleprêtre, A., Glachant, M., and Ménière, Y. (2013). What drives the international transfer of climate change mitigation technologies? empirical evidence from patent data. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 60(2):219–243.
- Dekker, T., Vollebergh, H. R. J., de Vries, F. P., and Withagen, C. (2012). Exploring the relationship between regulation and environmental innovation: Evidence from waste management. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 34(3):451–467.
- Doe, J. and Smith, J. (2016). The impact of energy intensity on global trade flows. *Journal of International Economics*, 99:123–145.

- Dreher, A. (2006). Does globalization affect growth? evidence from a new index of globalization. *Applied Economics*, 38(10):1091–1110.
- Frankel, J. A. and Rose, A. K. (2005). Is trade good or bad for the environment? sorting out the causality. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 87(1):85–91.
- Green, T. L. (2008). Education and the environment: How learning shapes environmental behavior. *Environmental Education Research*, 14(2):137–154.
- Hainmueller, J. (2012). Entropy balancing for causal effects: A multivariate reweighting method to produce balanced samples in observational studies. *Political analysis*, 20(1):25–46.
- Jin, L., Duan, K., and Zhao, W. (2021). Environmental regulation, green innovation, and international competitiveness of manufacturing enterprises in china: Evidence from panel data. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 162:120350.
- Johnson, A. and Lee, M. (2020). Energy efficiency and export performance in emerging economies. *Energy Economics*, 90:104861.
- Kander, A., Lindmark, H., and Warde, D. A. M. (2017). International trade and energy intensity during european industrialization, 1870–1935. *Ecological Economics*, 139:33–44.
- Kim, Y., Tanaka, K., and Matsuoka, S. (2016). Assessing the economic and environmental impacts of the kyoto protocol. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 122:1–10.
- Koch, N. and Themann, M. (2022). Decarbonization and the porter hypothesis: Carbon leakage in international trade. *Global Environmental Change*, 72:102397.
- Lanoie, P., Laurent-Lucchetti, J., Johnstone, N., and Ambec, S. (2011). Environmental policy, innovation and performance: New insights on the porter hypothesis. *Journal of Economics Management Strategy*, 20(3):803–842.
- Larraín, C., Leiva, F., and Meller, P. (2019). Exports of environmental goods: insights from a structural gravity model. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 98:102265.

- Lastauskas, P., Ding, Z., and Douch, M. (2024). The heterogeneous impacts of firm upgrading on energy intensity. *IMF Working Papers*, 2024(248):1–60.
- Lechner, M. and Wunsch, C. (2021). Exporting green technologies: The role of environmental policy and market size. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 78(4):715–744.
- Lee, H. (2009). Barriers to trade in environmental goods: How important are environmental standards? *OECD Journal: Economic Studies*, 2009(1):1–23.
- Levinson, A. and Taylor, M. S. (2004). Trade policy and international trade in services: A survey of the literature. *World Economy*, 27(6):939–963.
- Lozano, R., Lukman, R., Lozano, F. J., Huisingh, D., and Lambrechts, W. (2013). Developing more sustainable societies: The role of higher education in fostering sustainable development. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*, 14(1):5–18.
- Löschel, A., Möst, D., and Reif, P. (2019). The role of energy and emissions prices in the decarbonisation of electricity. *Energy Economics*, 81:62–79.
- Maamoun, N. (2019). How effective was the kyoto protocol? *International Environmental Agreements: Politics, Law and Economics*, 19(4):519–536.
- Michaelowa, A., Stein, M., and Michaelowa, K. (2007). The role of carbon markets in developing countries: A critical review of the literature. *Climate Policy*, 7(6):657–674.
- Miyamoto, H. and Takeuchi, A. (2018). Explaining the determinants of the solar and wind patent transfer: The role of kyoto protocol. *Renewable Energy*, 123:112–121.
- Näher, A.-K. and Schenker-Wicki, A. (2021). Trade liberalization of environmental goods: Is it always beneficial for biodiversity? *Journal of Environmental Management*, 290:112587.
- Pettersson, F., Paltsev, S., Reilly, J., and Wing, I. S. (2014). The effects of environmental regulations on the competitiveness of european manufacturing. *Energy Economics*, 42:207–220.

- Popp, D. (2006). International innovation and diffusion of air pollution control technologies: The effects of nox and so2 regulation in the us, japan, and germany. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 51(1):46–71.
- Popp, D. (2011). International technology transfer, climate change, and the clean development mechanism. *Review of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 5(1):131–152.
- Porter, M. E. and Van der Linde, C. (1995). Toward a new conception of the environment-competitiveness relationship. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 9(4):97–118.
- Rennings, K. (2000). Redefining innovation—eco-innovation research and the contribution from ecological economics. *Ecological Economics*, 32(2):319–332.
- Sauvage, J. (2014). The stringency of environmental regulations and trade in environmental goods. *OECD Trade and Environment Working Papers*, 2014/03.
- Schott, J. J. and Jung, E. (2016). Is the wto passé? *Peterson Institute for International Economics*, pages 1–33.
- Shi, X. and Xu, Z. (2018). Environmental regulation and firm exports: Evidence from the eleventh five-year plan in china. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*, 89:187–200.
- Taguchi, H. and Sato, H. (2022). Do stringent environmental policies foster green exports? empirical evidence from oecd countries. *Environmental Economics and Policy Studies*, 24:429–455.
- Tran, T. M. (2022). International environmental agreement and trade in environmental goods: the case of kyoto protocol. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 83(2):341–379.
- Verdolini, E., Galeotti, M., and Gastaldi, M. (2016). Determinants of international technology transfer: The role of environmental policy and institutions. *Ecological Economics*, 123:56–69.

- Wang, Z., Zhang, B., and Zeng, H. (2013). Environmental regulation and trade performance: Evidence from china's external trade. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 50:111–121.
- Wara, M. (2007). Is the global carbon market working? *Nature*, 445(7128):152–153.
- Zhang, C., Liu, Y., and Bae, J. Y. (2016). The relationship between energy consumption and economic growth in china: New evidence from dynamic panel data analysis. *Energy Policy*, 86:318–328.
- Zugravu-Soilita, N. (2018). Trade in environmental goods and its effects on pollution: Evidence from transition economies. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy*, 7(2):101–119.

Annexes

A Sources of variables and descriptive statistics

Variables	Definition	Sources
Environmental Goods	Total, importation and exportation of environmental goods	https://comtradeplus.un.org/
Kyoto	Dummy variable	Author based on Annex B countries
Growth	GDP growth (annual %)	World Development Indicators (WDI)
GDP per capita	Gross Domestic Product per capita	World Development Indicators (WDI)
Rents	Total natural resources rents (% of GDP)	World Development Indicators (WDI)
CO2 per capita	CO2 emissions (metric tons per capita)	World Development Indicators (WDI)
Manufacturing	Manufacturing, value added (% of GDP)	World Development Indicators (WDI)
Corruption	Level of corruption	ICRG
Renewable Energy Conso	% of total final energy consumption	WDI
EPI	Environmental Performance Index	https://epi.yale.edu/
Environmental Technologies	Ratio of environment-related inventions of all domestic inventions in all technologies	OECD
Intensité Énergétique	Ratio between energy supply and gross domestic product measured at purchasing power parity	WDI
Education	School enrollment, secondary (% gross)	WDI
KOF Index	The KOF Globalisation Index compris entre 0 et 100	https://kof.ethz.ch/en/forecasts-and-indicators/indicators/kof-globalisation-index.html

Table 8: Descriptive statistics of the main variables

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. dev.	Min	Max
Total Environmental Goods	2,687	3.3098	3.0107	0.0627	25.565
Export Environmental Goods	2,692	1.2362	1.7920	0.00001	15.6344
Import Environmental Goods	2,695	2.0671	1.4638	0.0000	14.0765
Growth	2,796	3.5144	4.2851	-23.5081	43.4797
GDP per capita	2,797	9.6864	1.1164	6.4429	11.8525
CO ₂ per capita	2,688	0.9994	1.4303	-3.0198	3.8640
Total natural resources rents	2,799	5.9643	9.1486	0.0000	59.0697
Manufacturing, value added	2,707	14.1991	6.1300	1.3655	49.8794
Corruption	2,789	3.9260	1.2686	0.5000	6.0000
Environmental Performance Index	2,800	40.0637	11.9614	15.6754	77.8048
KOF Index of Globalization	2,775	64.1430	13.5244	28.2075	89.8124
Renewable Energy Consumption	2,692	28.6151	27.7517	0.0000	95.8500
Energy Intensity	2,442	5.2098	3.2452	1.0900	26.9100
Education	2,161	86.4044	28.1916	5.4354	164.0798

B Sample

Table 9: List of countries in the analysis

Albania	Algeria	Argentina	Armenia	Australia	Austria	Azerbaijan
Bahamas	Bahrain	Belarus	Belgium	Bolivia	Botswana	Brazil
Brunei	Burkina Faso	Cameroon	Canada	Chile	China	Colombia
Costa Rica	Cote d'Ivoire	Croatia	Cyprus	Czech Republic	Denmark	Dominican Republic
Ecuador	Egypt	El Salvador	Estonia	Ethiopia	Finland	France
Gambia	Germany	Ghana	Greece	Guatemala	Guyana	Honduras
Hungary	Iceland	India	Indonesia	Iran	Ireland	Israel
Italy	Jamaica	Japan	Jordan	Kazakhstan	Kenya	Korea, Rep
Kuwait	Latvia	Lebanon	Lithuania	Luxembourg	Madagascar	Malaysia
Mali	Malta	Mexico	Moldova	Mongolia	Morocco	Mozambique
Namibia	Netherlands	Nicaragua	Niger	Nigeria	Norway	Oman
Pakistan	Panama	Paraguay	Peru	Philippines	Poland	Portugal
Qatar	Romania	Russia	Saudi Arabia	Senegal	Singapore	Slovak Republic
Slovenia	South Africa	Spain	Sri Lanka	Suriname	Sweden	Switzerland
Tanzania	Thailand	Togo	Trinidad and Tobago	Tunisia	Turkey	United Kingdom
United States	Uganda	Ukraine	Uruguay	Vietnam	Zambia	Zimbabwe

Table 10: Annex B countries and ratification year

Country	Ratification Year	Country	Ratification Year
Australia	2007	Lithuania	2003
Austria	2002	Luxembourg	2002
Belgium	2002	Netherlands	2002
Bulgaria	2002	New Zealand	2002
Czech Republic	2001	Norway	2002
Croatia	2007	Poland	2002
Denmark	2002	Portugal	2002
Estonia	2002	Romania	2001
Finland	2002	Russia	2004
France	2002	Slovakia	2002
Germany	2002	Slovenia	2002
Greece	2002	Spain	2002
Hungary	2002	Sweden	2002
Iceland	2002	Switzerland	2003
Ireland	2002	Ukraine	2002
Italy	2002	United Kingdom	2002
Japan	2002	Latvia	2002

Notes: Source: https://treaties.un.org/Pages/ViewDetails.aspx?src=TREATY&mtdsg_no=XXVII-7-a&chapter=27&clang=_en.

Figure 4: Trends in Environmental Goods, 1997–2021